

The Role of Computer Literacy Familiarity in the Adoption of e-Government by Public Sector Workers in Local Government Authorities: A Case of Kigamboni Municipal Council

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Abstract:

Public sector workplaces, including local government authorities, have adopted e-Government in recent years to improve service delivery, enhance transparency, and foster citizen engagement. The objective of this research is to examine the impact of computer literacy on e-Government adoption in local government authorities in Tanzania with the focus being on the Kigamboni Municipal Council. A study is conducted to examine how computer literacy familiarity among public sector workers in local government authorities influences the adoption of e-Government. The study adopted the mixed method approach which involves both quantitative and qualitative data. The data was thus collected using

interviews and questionnaires with the target population being employees at Kigamboni Municipal Council. Data was analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. It is established in the research that the level of computer literacy and familiarity with technology among public sector workers plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of e-Government implementation. Inferential analysis showed that computer literacy drives e-government adoption. Computer literacy's impact on e-government adoption has a mean of 3.27 and a standard deviation of 1.26. E-government usage is similarly affected by computer proficiency, with a mean of 4.5 and SD of 1.40. Computer training is also essential for e-government adoption (Mean; 3.8 SD; 1.34). Computer literacy is both a crucial factor in e-government adoption and a key obstacle at Kigamboni Municipal Council (Mean; 3.1 and SD 1.41). This finding indicates that it would be advantageous for the government to continue implementing training programs with the goal of improving the skills of a majority of participants in utilizing e-Government platforms. The efficacy of e-Government implementation is heavily influenced by the extent of computer literacy and technological proficiency exhibited by public sector employees. The research findings also suggest that the degree of computer literacy possessed by an individual plays a crucial role in determining their proficiency in utilizing e-Government platforms and services. This proficiency encompasses various activities, including conducting transactions, using systems and accessing information via websites and portals. This finding suggests that there are potential benefits for the government in maintaining the implementation of training programs aimed at enhancing the proficiency of a majority of participants in utilizing e-government platforms.

Keywords: *Computer literacy, Local government authorities, Public sector workers, e-Government and Public sector.*

Introduction

The emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has resulted in substantial transformations in the functioning and provision of services by governments to their constituents. Tanzania, similar to numerous other developing nations, has acknowledged the potential of electronic government (e-Government) in enhancing governance and the provision of services. In 2012, the Tanzanian government established an e-Government agency tasked with the coordination, supervision, and provision of e-Government initiatives. This agency is also responsible for enforcing e-Government standards across various entities, including Tanzania Ministries, Departments, Agencies, and Local Government Authorities (Kisoka, 2022). Over the past few years, the Tanzanian government has introduced a number of e-Government initiatives with the aim of improving the delivery of public services, promoting transparency, and enhancing administrative procedures (Kanyika et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the implementation and utilization of e-Government systems within local government authorities continue to exhibit a relatively low level of adoption among public sector employees.

In the contemporary working environment, public sector employees are expected to possess a comprehensive understanding of computer technology in order to actively engage and contribute to their professional roles. Al Sayegh et al., (2023) noted that the level of computer literacy among the population plays a significant role in the effectiveness of electronic government implementation. The Tanzanian government has been proactively implementing electronic government (e-Government) initiatives with the aim of improving the effectiveness, openness, and availability of public services. The National ICT Policy and e-Government Strategy serve as a comprehensive framework for the implementation of e-Government initiatives and aim to foster the utilization of digital technologies in the provision of government services (Kanyika et al.,

2021). A number of e-Government platforms have been devised and put into operation, such as the Government Electronic Payment Gateway (GePG) for facilitating online payment of government services, the Tanzania National ID System (NIDA) for the purpose of citizen identification, and the Tanzania Immigration e-service portal for handling passport and visa application.

Rodríguez-Hevía et al., (2020) noted that the adoption and utilization of e-Government systems are significantly influenced by computer literacy (Maphangwa and Dwivedi, 2018). Computer literacy encompasses the acquisition and mastery of knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for proficient utilization of computer technology. It encompasses fundamental computer operations, utilization of the internet, and proficiency in diverse software applications. In the realm of e-Government, possessing computer literacy is imperative for public sector employees in order to effectively navigate digital platforms, access online services, and execute administrative duties with proficiency. Nevertheless, recent research conducted by Charles (2020) established that the computer literacy levels among public sector employees in Tanzania are insufficient. The adoption and effective utilization of e-Government systems are impeded by individuals' limited computer literacy skills (Charles, 2020). This has been widely recognized as a means of addressing the current state of affairs in the public sector. Moreover, the limited acceptance of e-Government systems among individuals employed in the public sector can be ascribed to various factors that extend beyond proficiency in computer usage. The adoption behavior is influenced by various factors, including perceptions of usefulness and ease of use, organizational support, and the availability of technical infrastructure and support.

The local government authorities are one of the government agencies that have been granted authority in the pursuit of e-Government. Despite concerted efforts to promote e-Government initiatives in Tanzania, there exists

a dearth of comprehension regarding the significance of computer literacy in shaping the acceptance and utilization of e-Government systems among public sector employees within local government authorities. Multiple scholarly investigations have underscored the significance of computer literacy in effectively embracing and employing e-Government systems (Kisoka, 2022). Nonetheless, a research gap exists concerning the precise influence of computer literacy among public sector employees on the adoption of e-Government within Tanzanian local government authorities. Furthermore, prior research has predominantly concentrated on overarching determinants that impact the adoption of e-Government, such as perceived utility and user-friendliness (Ekanem and Kim, 2023). The examination of the distinct difficulties encountered by public sector employees with limited computer literacy in effectively utilizing e-Government systems within the specific context of Local Government Authorities (LGAs) is imperative. Hence, this research investigates the influence of computer literacy among employees in the public sector on the implementation of e-Government in local government authorities in Tanzania, specifically examining the Kigamboni Municipal Council as a representative case study. It is imperative to comprehend the influence of computer literacy on the adoption of e-Government in Local Government Authorities (LGAs) in Tanzania. This understanding is essential for the identification of obstacles, the formulation of efficient strategies, and the advancement of inclusivity in the realm of digital governance. The main objective of the research is thus to assess how computer literacy impacts e-Government adoption in local government authorities with a focus on Kigamboni Municipal Council.

Literature Review

According to Kisera (2018), it was determined that there exists a requirement for customized training programs that are designed to address the unique job tasks and responsibilities of workers. This study emphasizes the necessity of

implementing training programs that are tailored to address the distinct requirements of public sector employees and their respective job responsibilities. Furthermore, it emphasizes the significance of managerial support in fostering computer literacy abilities among personnel in the public sector. The aforementioned findings align with prior research that has underscored the significance of training and support in enhancing computer literacy abilities among employees in the public sector. In their study, Mmari and Kissaka (2019) discovered that the introduction of e-Government in Dodoma City Council encountered various obstacles. These issues encompassed a deficiency in computer proficiency among public sector employees, insufficient allocation of resources, and a dearth of political determination. The study suggests that it is necessary to offer training and capacity building initiatives for employees in the public sector, allocate more funds in the budget for the implementation of e-Government, and strengthen the political determination to ensure successful implementation.

According to the study conducted by Mohammed and Mbowe (2017), it was observed that the computer literacy level among teachers in Tanzania was rather poor. The findings indicated that a tiny proportion of instructors possessed fundamental computer abilities. The study additionally revealed that a significant proportion of educators had not undergone any structured instruction pertaining to computer literacy. The study suggests that it is necessary for the government and other relevant parties to offer training and capacity building initiatives to educators in order to improve their proficiency in computer literacy. The report also suggests that it is imperative for the government to allocate funds towards enhancing computer infrastructure in educational institutions, thereby enabling teachers to avail themselves of computers and other technical resources.

Rugaimukamu (2017) conducted a study that found that the utilization of computers among primary school educators in Tanzania yielded favorable outcomes, such as heightened efficacy in lesson preparation, higher pedagogical abilities, and heightened levels of motivation.

The research additionally discovered that the utilization of computers presented several difficulties, including insufficient proficiency in computer usage and restricted availability of computer resources. The study suggests that it is imperative for the government to allocate resources towards the development of computer infrastructure and the implementation of training and capacity-building initiatives for educators, with the aim of augmenting their proficiency in computer literacy. The study further suggests the necessity of addressing the issues related to computer utilization in educational institutions in order to optimize the potential advantages of computer use on instructors' efficacy. The research conducted by Geoffrey and Mosha (2018) demonstrated that various factors, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, and social influence, exerted a substantial impact on the adoption of e-Government services in Tanzania. The research additionally discovered that variables such as internet connectivity, computer proficiency, and computer accessibility constituted notable obstacles to the utilization of e-Government services. The study suggests that there is a necessity for governmental intervention in order to expand internet access, invest in computer infrastructure, and implement training and capacity building initiatives to promote computer literacy abilities. The study additionally suggests that it is imperative for the government to resolve the obstacles hindering the utilization of e-Government services in order to enhance the adoption of such services among Tanzanian citizens. According to the findings of Yared and Jumanne (2019), several factors, including insufficient ICT infrastructure, restricted financial resources, and inadequate training and capacity-building initiatives, emerged as notable obstacles to the implementation of ICT in higher education institutions. The study suggests that it is imperative for institutions of higher education to allocate resources towards the development of information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure. Additionally, it is recommended that these institutions offer training and capacity-building programs to strengthen the computer literacy abilities of their

students. Furthermore, the establishment of policies and strategies to encourage the integration of ICT into teaching and learning processes is deemed necessary.

Materials and Methods

Area of the Study

Tanzania's Kigamboni Municipal Council served as the study's area of study. After Tanzania implemented the Decentralization Policy, Kigamboni was first established as a Municipality in 2015. The Temeke Municipal Council oversaw the region that included the Kigamboni District Jurisdiction until 2015.

Research Design

The research design employed in this study was the exploratory research design. The exploratory research design is a form of research design that seeks to investigate a topic that is relatively unfamiliar or inadequately comprehended. The utilization of this approach is prevalent throughout the initial phases of a research endeavor when the researcher seeks to acquire a more profound comprehension of the topic matter or engender novel thoughts and perspectives. The exploratory research design is a research methodology that primarily concentrates on the exploration of a certain subject or issue with the aim of acquiring a more profound comprehension, generating novel insights, and formulating preliminary ideas or hypotheses.

Research Approach

This study utilized a mixed method approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods in its research approach. The rationale for employing this methodology is rooted in the imperative to acquire a comprehensive comprehension of the influence of computer literacy on the adoption of e-Government within the context of public sector employees in Tanzanian local government authorities. The integration of quantitative and qualitative methodologies in the research approach facilitates a more comprehensive and holistic comprehension of the intricate correlation

between computer literacy and e-Government adoption among public sector workers in Local Government Authorities (LGAs). This study focused on the Kigamboni Municipal Council located in Tanzania.

Targeted Population

The targeted population for this study was public sector workers in Kigamboni Municipal Council in Tanzania. This population was chosen because they are directly involved in the implementation and delivery of e-Government services at the local government level.

Sample Size

The sample size was determined using the formula for calculating sample size for a finite population, which is:

$$n = N / (1 + N(e^2)) \quad (1)$$

where:

n = Sample size

N = Total population size

e = Level of precision, set at 7% (0.07)

Using the total staff population of 219 and a level of precision of 7%, the calculation for the sample size is as follows:

$$n = 219 / (1 + 219(0.07^2))$$

$$n = 105.8$$

Therefore, a sample size of 105 public sector workers is appropriate for this study, as it provides a representative sample of the total population while ensuring adequate participation and representation.

Sampling Strategies

The researcher used simple random sampling, assigning a unique identifier to each population member using a label system. Respondents were presented with papers written as NO or Yes, with those who chose the label YES being

eligible for the study, and those who chose NO were excluded. The researcher had no control over selecting specific respondents for the study.

Data Collection Tool

The collection of quantitative data was conducted by means of questionnaires. The questionnaires were disseminated through the utilization of Google online forms. Qualitative data collection in the study was conducted through the utilization of interviews. The acquisition of abundant qualitative data was facilitated through the implementation of individual or group interviews with carefully chosen participants. This method enabled the researchers to pose probing questions, thereby facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences.

Data Analysis

Within the quantitative paradigm, the process of data analysis encompasses the utilization of statistical methodologies to systematically arrange, condense, and derive meaning from the collected data. The descriptive analysis in this study was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 26. The qualitative methodology involved the analysis of data obtained through interviews or open-ended survey questions. This analysis employed thematic analysis, which entailed the systematic examination of a dataset to identify recurring patterns and extract meaningful themes.

Validity and Reliability

In quantitative research, Cronbach's alpha coefficient measured internal consistency and data reliability. A pilot study tested interview question clarity, comprehensibility, and consistency in qualitative research to assure dependability. Pilot study feedback will improve the questionnaire. A questionnaire based on known study tools and face validity verified quantitative research validity. For quantitative data, construct validity was tested by testing instrument accuracy in capturing the construct of interest. The questionnaire measured depression markers. Comparing qualitative research findings with secondary data from

literature reviews confirmed similarities and differences. Research reliability, validity, and validity are critical to study success.

Results

Table 1. Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.994	.994	18

Source: research data

Table 2. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy		0.883
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	729.827
	Df	122
	Sig.	0

Source: research data

Based on the analysis, it is established of the reliability of the instruments adopted in the research.

The research analyzed the demographic profile of respondents, revealing that 7% were aged 18-24, 21% were aged 25-34, 38% were aged 35-44, 24% were aged 45-54, and 10% were aged 55-60. The majority were female, with 38% being female and 62% male. The education level of respondents was assessed, with 79% having a bachelor's degree, 13% having a master's degree, and 2% having a PHD degree. The work duration of respondents at the ministry was also assessed, with 77% working less than one year, 21% working 1 to 3 years, 30% working 4 to 6 years, 20% working 7 to 10 years, and 4% working more than 15 years.

Table 3. Demographic profile

		Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-24	6	7
	25-34	18	21
	35-44	33	38
	45-54	21	24
	Over 55	9	10
	Total	87	100
Gender	Male	54	62
	Female	33	38
	Total	87	100
Education Background	Ordinary diploma	5	6
	Bachelor's degree	69	79
	Master's degree	11	13
	PHD	2	2
	Total	87	100
Work duration	Less than 1 year	17	20
	1-3	29	33
	4-6	20	23
	7-10	21	24
	Total	87	100

Source: research data (2023)

The present study assessed the perspectives of participants regarding the significance of computer literacy familiarity in facilitating the successful adoption of e-Government initiatives. Based on the collected data, it has been determined that a significant majority of the respondents, specifically 88%, expressed agreement regarding the significance of possessing a certain level of computer literacy in order to facilitate the successful adoption of e-Government initiatives. A total of 2% of the respondents expressed a neutral stance, neither agreeing nor disagreeing, while 10% of the respondents indicated disagreement. Therefore, it can be inferred that possessing a certain level of computer literacy is crucial for the successful implementation of e-Government initiatives. The findings are succinctly outlined in table 3. The objective of the study was to determine the impact of computer literacy on the proficiency of individuals in utilizing e-Government platforms and services. This encompasses activities such as conducting transactions and retrieving information via online platforms and portals. Based on the data that was gathered, it has been determined that 90% of the participants expressed agreement, whereas 8% of the participants expressed disagreement. A total of 2% of the participants maintained a neutral stance regarding the matter.

Table 4. Computer Literacy Familiarity

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	65	75
Agree	11	13
Neither agree nor disagree	2	2
Disagree	6	7
Strongly disagree	3	3
Total	87	100

Source: research data

Based on this finding, it can be concluded that a majority of the participants acknowledged the

substantial impact of computer literacy on their proficiency in utilizing e-Government platforms and services. The findings are succinctly outlined in Table 4. The study also aimed to determine the perceptions of the participants regarding the feasibility of adopting and utilizing e-Government services by enhancing the computer literacy skills of public employees in local government authorities in Tanzania. The findings derived from the analysis revealed that 76% of the participants expressed agreement with the statement, whereas 21% of the participants indicated disagreement with the statement. Furthermore, a total of 3% of the participants expressed neither agreement nor disagreement with the statement, indicating their neutral stance on the matter. The analysis reveals a clear consensus among the majority of respondents in agreement with the statement. The findings are succinctly presented in table 5.

Table 5. Proficiency

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	40	46
Agree	38	44
Neither agree nor disagreed	2	2
Disagree	4	5
Strongly disagreed	3	3
Total	87	100

Source: research data

Table 6. Feasibility

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	39	45
Agree	27	31
Neither agree nor disagreed	3	3
Disagree	10	12
Strongly disagreed	8	9
Total	87	100

Source: research data

Table 6. Inferential analysis

Item statistics	N	Mean	SD	Overall rating
Computer literacy is important in the successful adoption of e-government	87	3.27	1.26	Strongly agree
Computer proficiency level impacts affects e-government usage	87	4.5	1.40	Agree
Computer training among employees is important in e-government adoption	87	3.8	1.34	Agree
Computer literacy remains a challenge in the adoption of e-government at Kigamboni council	87	3.1	1.41	Strongly agree

Source: research data

Further inferential analysis established that computer literacy plays a key role in the adoption of e-government. Mean of 3.27 and standard deviation of 1.26 is established in the analysis of the significance of computer literacy in the successful adoption of e-government. Similarly, a mean of 4.5 and SD of 1.40 is also established signaling that computer proficiency level impacts affects e-government usage. Computer training is also established as a key element in the adoption of e-government (Mean; 3.8 SD; 1.34). while computer literacy is established to play a key role in the adoption of e-government, it is also established to be a key challenge in the adoption of e-government at Kigamboni Municipal council (Mean; 3.1 and SD 1.41). This is as summarized in table 6.

In the thematic analysis, it is also evident that computer literacy plays a key role in the adoption of e-government in the LGAs. The first theme evident is digital skills and competency. Computer literacy determines the level of digital skills and competency that public sector workers possess. Those with higher computer literacy are more likely to adapt to e-government tools, navigate digital interfaces, and effectively use various online platforms and services. The second theme established is ease of learning and training: Employees with better computer literacy will find it easier to learn and adapt to new e-government systems. They require less training and are more self-sufficient in exploring and using new technology tools, making the implementation of e-government initiatives smoother. The third theme established is overcoming resistance to change. Some public sector workers may be resistant to change, especially when it involves technology adoption. Higher computer literacy reduces the fear and resistance associated with using new digital

systems and fosters a positive attitude towards e-government implementation.

Discussion

The research aimed to examine the impact of computer literacy on the adoption of e-Government among public sector employees in Local Government Authorities. According to Griffen et al., (2022), the contemporary landscape has witnessed a significant transformation in the manner in which governments engage with their constituents, owing to the widespread adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs). The utilization of electronic government (e-Government) has emerged as a potent mechanism for augmenting the provision of public services, promoting transparency, and improving operational effectiveness. The successful implementation of e-Government is contingent upon the level of computer literacy and familiarity with technology among public sector workers.

e-Government refers to the utilization of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in order to enhance the provision of public services and facilitate the government's engagement with citizens and businesses (Nugraha and Susanto, 2022). In the context of Tanzania, the implementation of e-Government presents significant opportunities for the optimization of administrative procedures, the mitigation of corrupt practices, the enhancement of transparency, and the promotion of citizen participation. The utilization of this technology has the potential to revolutionize the manner in which public services are administered, ultimately resulting in enhanced results for the

populace. It is important to note that certain Local Government Authorities (LGAs) have made notable advancements in the digitalization of services, whereas others are facing obstacles that have resulted in slower progress. These challenges encompass a range of factors, one of which is the limited level of computer literacy among public sector employees (Charles, 2020).

According to the findings of Nokele and Mukonza (2021), computer literacy encompasses the proficiency in utilizing computers and associated technologies to effectively accomplish diverse tasks. In the realm of e-Government implementation, the acquisition of computer literacy by public sector employees assumes paramount importance as it enables them to effectively navigate digital platforms, access and analyze data, and engage in efficient online interactions with citizens. The significance of possessing a certain level of computer literacy in order to facilitate successful implementation of e-Government initiatives has been well-documented in existing scholarly literature. This aligns with the findings of Samuel et al., (2020), which suggest that public sector employees who possess advanced computer literacy skills are capable of effectively managing and providing services via online platforms. As a consequence, this phenomenon engenders expedited response durations and enhanced service excellence for individuals within the community.

A subsequent inquiry revealed that the majority of participants expressed a high level of comfort with the digital technologies and applications employed within e-Government systems. Nevertheless, a significant proportion of the participants have also expressed discomfort with the aforementioned systems. This observation suggests that it would be beneficial for the government to develop strategies aimed at improving the user experience and satisfaction of individuals utilizing e-government systems. According to Samuel et al., (2020), the implementation of digital technologies can optimize bureaucratic processes by minimizing the reliance on physical paperwork and manual execution of tasks. Workers with proficiency in computer skills have the ability to utilize e-

Government systems in order to automate various processes, resulting in heightened levels of operational efficiency.

The research also demonstrates that one's proficiency in computer literacy has a notable impact on their capacity to proficiently utilize e-Government platforms and services, including engaging in transactions and accessing information via websites and portals. E-Government platforms have the potential to augment transparency through the provision of accessible information and data (Kiattikunwong, 2022). Employees with proficiency in computer skills possess the ability to effectively administer and revise these platforms, thereby guaranteeing the provision of precise and current information to members of the public. The utilization of e-Government enables citizens to actively engage in decision-making processes. Public sector workers who possess computer literacy skills have the ability to enhance these interactions and actively involve citizens by utilizing digital channels. The research findings indicate that a significant proportion of the respondents possess the necessary skills to effectively communicate and collaborate with other government agencies through digital channels. However, it is noteworthy that a considerable number of respondents also expressed a lack of proficiency in this area.

This finding suggests that it would be beneficial for the government to persist in the implementation of training programs aimed at enhancing the proficiency of a majority of the participants in utilizing e-government platforms. The research also confirms that possessing computer literacy skills plays a crucial role in determining the level of data management, analysis, and privacy within e-Government initiatives. This phenomenon is particularly evident when it is additionally confirmed that a majority of the personnel within the Local Government Authorities (LGAs) utilize computer systems and similar technological devices, such as laptops, to carry out their professional responsibilities. According to previous studies, the Tanzanian government has implemented training programs in order to support the e-government initiatives.

Nevertheless, a considerable proportion of the survey participants remain uninformed regarding the technology regulatory frameworks in place within the nation that oversee e-government endeavors.

The significance of computer literacy proficiency among public sector employees in Tanzanian Local Government Authorities has been widely acknowledged as a pivotal determinant in the effective implementation of e-Government initiatives. However, it has been determined that the Local Government Authorities (LGAs) in Tanzania continue to encounter certain obstacles, notably a lack of proficiency in the execution of e-government initiatives. Through the implementation of strategies aimed at overcoming obstacles and allocating resources towards education and skill development, the Tanzanian government has the potential to cultivate a conducive atmosphere wherein e-Government is seamlessly integrated into the provision of public services. This integration would subsequently result in enhanced operational effectiveness, heightened transparency, and increased citizen participation. The adoption of digital transformation will facilitate the establishment of a government in Tanzania that is more interconnected and capable of promptly addressing societal needs.

Conclusion

The findings of the study have demonstrated that possessing a strong foundation in computer literacy familiarity is of utmost importance in facilitating the successful adoption of e-Government initiatives. A proficient level of computer literacy is essential for public sector employees in order to efficiently process and deliver services through online platforms. Consequently, the provision of services to citizens is enhanced, leading to improved responsiveness and reduced waiting times. Subsequent to this inquiry, it was ascertained that a significant proportion of participants exhibited familiarity with the software and digital tools employed by e-Government services. Nevertheless, a considerable proportion of the participants expressed a sense of discomfort

when utilizing the aforementioned devices. This implies that there is a need for the government to implement strategies aimed at enhancing user satisfaction with e-government platforms. The digitization of operations has the potential to expedite bureaucratic procedures by reducing the reliance on paperwork and manual labor. Workers who possess computer literacy skills have the ability to utilize e-Government systems in order to automate various processes, thereby resulting in enhanced operational efficiency.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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